

Report C

Advances in neurodegenerative diseases

The situation in Spain

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Production process

Reports C are brief documents on subjects chosen by the Bureau of the Congress of Deputies that contextualise and summarise the available scientific evidence on the analysed subject. They also inform about areas of agreement, disagreement, unknowns, and ongoing discussions. The preparation process for these reports is based on an exhaustive bibliographical review, complemented with interviews of experts in the field who subsequently conduct two review rounds of the text. Oficina C conducts this process in collaboration with the management team of the Spanish Parliament's Lower House Documentation, Library and Archive service.

To produce this report the C Office referenced 273 documents and consulted 21 experts in the subject. Of this multi-disciplinary group, 33.3% come from the field of social sciences (psychology, economics), 61.9% are from life sciences (biochemistry, medicine and nursing) and 4.8% are from engineering. 90.5% work in Spanish institutions or centres, whereas 9.5% have affiliations abroad.

Oficina C is responsible for publication of this report.

RSV has received personal payments in the last 3 years for participation on advisory boards for Lilly, Novo-Nordisk, Grifols-Araclon, Aviadobio, Preval, Wave Pharmaceuticals and Pfizer on products under research that are not currently approved or on the market.

MSC has undertaken consultation and advisory roles for Roche Diagnostics International Ltd and Grifols S.L. He was awarded a project funded by Roche Diagnostics International Ltd. All of the fees were paid to his institution (BBRC). Through his institution he has received support in kind for research for the following companies: ADx Neurosciences, Roche Diagnostics International Ltd, Avid Radiopharmaceuticals, Inc. Eli Lilly and Janssen Research & Development. He has participated in symposia sponsored by Ammiral, Eli Lilly, Novo Nordisk, Roche Diagnostics and Roche Farma.

Summary C

The report in 5 minutes

Neurodegenerative diseases involve the nervous system, are incapacitating and, to date, incurable. Between 1 and 1.5 million people are affected by these diseases, which entail a high personal, social and financial cost. In addition, the risk of suffering Alzheimer's, Parkinson's or amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) multiply with age, which means that increased life expectancy implies a very significant increase in cases. Conversely, other diseases included in this report such as Huntington's or multiple sclerosis present at an earlier age. Their earlier onset results in the difficulties typical of these life stages, such as a loss of productivity, extends the duration of the disease, and multiplies possibilities of being discriminated against and stigmatised.

There is still no European plan for these diseases, the Spanish National Health System's Neurodegenerative Diseases Strategy dates from 2016, and the National Plan on Alzheimer's and other dementias finishes this year. Experts have voiced their concern about the urgent need to plan public, social and healthcare policies that guarantee the protection of this most vulnerable sector of the population.

This report provides a summary of current knowledge about the most prevalent neurodegenerative diseases, and includes information about their causes, risk factors, current state of diagnosis and treatments, in addition to describing adaptations of social services and the healthcare system necessary to face the challenge.

Neurodegenerative diseases

Except for multiple sclerosis, which is related to inflammatory processes mediated by the immune system, it is believed that neurodegenerative diseases have their origin in dysfunctional proteins that accumulate over many years, causing diverse problems of toxicity and death in brain and spinal cord neurons.

Neural cell death brings a progressive loss of cognitive and motor functions. Each disease follows a different course because each affects different types of neurons. But in all of these diseases, mild onset symptoms worsen as neural deterioration progresses. In some instances, like Alzheimer's and the majority of Parkinson's cases, cognitive deterioration manifests in the final phase of the disease, presenting a set of symptoms known as dementia.

With the exception of Huntington's and cases of familial origin for which the causes are exclusively genetic, in most cases the risk of developing these diseases is influenced by the interaction of genetic, environmental and lifestyle factors over time, although we still do not know all of the aspects involved.

Focal point

As neurodegenerative diseases take years to evolve, changing some lifestyle habits or reducing the risk factors at given stages of life may reduce the risk of developing this kind of disease. It is estimated that over a third of all dementia cases could be preventable.

When symptoms appear, these diseases are not usually detected at an early stage. Although the diagnosis can be a serious setback for the patient and their family, there are also many medical and social advantages, if the necessary support is available from the start to manage the negative feelings that arise and obtain resources to cope with the disease.

Although there are no specific techniques for all neurodegenerative diseases, Alzheimer's can be diagnosed with lumbar puncture (spinal tap) or positron emission tomography whereas Huntington's is confirmed with genetic testing. Researchers have recently developed a highly effective technique to detect Parkinson's during its early stages using samples of cerebrospinal fluid. In the future, detection of Alzheimer's and other diseases could be based on a simple blood test.

There are highly effective treatments that hold back multiple sclerosis, stopping inflammation before the onset of neural damage. The most incapacitating symptoms of Parkinson's disease can be controlled using pharmacological therapies (levodopa and others), and surgical (deep brain stimulation) or non-invasive treatments such as high-intensity focused ultrasound. However, effective treatments are still necessary for Huntington's disease, ALS, Alzheimer's and other causes of dementia. To achieve this aim, we need to improve the transfer of outcomes in research into these diseases to clinical practice.

Although new drugs that can hold back the progression of Alzheimer's for some months are a great step forward, Europe is debating their benefit risk ratio.

Some experts also question the safety and effectiveness of certain psychopharmaceuticals for people with dementia.

On the other hand, cognitive stimulation therapies have the support of scientific evidence and are cost-effective, although there is not equal access to them throughout Spain. Other therapies such as physiotherapy, speech and language therapy, occupational therapy or early access to palliative care can improve the quality of life of people with neurodegenerative diseases, although access to these services is not the same in each autonomous community.

On the horizon

To improve equality, medical professionals highlight the need for a distribution of resources to achieve sufficient regional coverage, and the advisability of establishing robust inter-hospital referral systems. They also suggest that planning would be made easier with patient registries and emphasise the importance of training for primary care professionals in these diseases, in addition to increasing the number of specialist personnel.

On the other hand, social costs are higher than those of medical care and this increases with the severity and length of the disease. It is families that bear most of the burden, which highlights the need to develop a system of sustainable, professional specialist care.

The current stance is to foster the social inclusion of patients, allowing them to remain at home for as long as possible with the support of technologies and carers. However, when people with dementia cannot live at home anymore, alternatives exist, such as unidades de convivencia (“coexistence units”) and other options already firmly established in other European countries. Associations representing ALS and Huntington’s call for the creation of care centres specialised in these diseases.

The comprehensive care requires greater coordination between the social and healthcare sectors to improve the inclusion and well-being of patients and their families

Advances in neurodegenerative diseases

Introduction

The most notably prevalent neurodegenerative diseases are Alzheimer's and other disorders that cause cognitive deterioration and dementia. These are followed by Parkinson's, multiple sclerosis (of autoimmune origin) amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) and Huntington's disease.

All of these diseases cause neural cell death, with consequent cognitive and motor disability. They reduce the life expectancy of patients and are, to date, incurable.

The term neurodegenerative diseases covers over 600 different disorders; however, among the most notable due to their [prevalence](#) and severity, are Alzheimer's and other causes of dementia, Parkinson's, multiple sclerosis, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), and Huntington's' (**Key Point 1**). The risk of suffering one of these diseases rises exponentially with age, which is why increased life expectancy will bring a rise in the number of cases. Thus, the worldwide population with dementia is expected to have practically tripled by the year 2050, whereas projections for Spain estimate an 83% increase, which will mean 1.5 million cases². Moreover, for reasons that are still unknown, Parkinson's is probably the neurodegenerative disease whose [incidence](#) has most increased in recent decades³ and its figures are expected to duplicate by 2030⁴. It is calculated that the number of ALS patients will have risen 69% worldwide by 2040⁵.

What all of these diseases have in common is that they are chronic, and their progression brings a gradual dysfunction of the nervous system¹. Brain and spinal cord neurons undergo changes that cause their abnormal functioning and, ultimately, cell death⁶. Each disease is characterised by initially affecting different types of neurons, which causes different symptoms¹. Although their onset occurs in a specific region, as time passes, they gradually spread throughout the whole nervous system⁷. During early phases, the symptoms are usually mild and go unnoticed. However, as neural deterioration progresses, they become more severe, generating disability⁶. Currently, these diseases are incurable and reduce the life expectancy of the people who have them⁶. Indeed, they are a source of concern for most of the Spanish population, who consider them to be a serious or very serious health problem⁸. These disorders were also the most common cause for people to request and undergo euthanasia (117 deaths) in 2022. Within this group, 41.9% had ALS, 11.1% multiple sclerosis and 8.5% Parkinson's⁹.

In this context, experts have voiced the urgent need to plan public policies that adapt the health and social welfare systems to this silent epidemic². However, to date there is no European plan covering this area. In Spain, the National Health System's Neurodegenerative Diseases Strategy, which dates from 2016, is currently under review¹. Experts note that the National Plan on Alzheimer's and other dementias, which finishes this year¹⁰, lacks both funding and impact.

· [Prevalence](#): the total number of people within a population who have or had a disease.
· [Incidence](#): the number of new cases of a disease.

Although the definition of neurodegenerative diseases refers to disorders involving the central nervous system, other disorders cause cell death in the peripheral nervous system, muscles or sensory organs. Another type are transmissible neurodegenerative diseases caused by prions.

Key point 1. Other neurodegenerative diseases

Although the classic definition of neurodegenerative diseases includes those that involve the [central nervous system](#), in other cases, degeneration affects different cell types, such as the peripheral nervous system (this is the case of neuropathies of the Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease group of conditions or familial amyloid polyneuropathy) the neuromuscular junction (myasthenia gravis) myocytes (muscular dystrophies such as Duchenne muscular dystrophy, limb-girdle muscular dystrophies, Steinert disease or congenital myopathies)¹¹. These are rare conditions, but there are around 60,000 people in Spain¹² who have them. These diseases are hereditary and affect children and young people the most¹³⁻¹⁷.

There are also disorders where degeneration may occur in sensory organs like eyes or ears. Some examples are retinitis pigmentosa, diabetic retinopathy or age-related macular degeneration, which is the main cause of geriatric blindness worldwide and affects some 700,000 people in Spain^{18,19}.

Another type of neurodegenerative disorders are human transmissible spongiform encephalopathies, like Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease²⁰. They are caused by infectious agents called [prions](#) and, although uncommon, are categorised as reportable and are always fatal²⁰. Animals that may be their focus of transmission are monitored by the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food²¹.

The most prevalent neurodegenerative diseases

The risk of having a neurodegenerative disease increases with age.

The symptoms of multiple sclerosis and Huntington's disease, which is hereditary, first appear in younger people.

Description of the diseases

Alzheimer's disease and other dementias

Figures for Spain in 2019 estimated between 734,000 and 937,000 cases of dementia². This is the most frequent neurodegenerative disorder, affects more women than men² and its incidence exponentially increases from 65-70 years of age, although it may appear in younger people¹.

The term dementia is used to refer to a group of symptoms that include difficulties with memory or language, and the loss of problem-solving skills to an extent that prevents the patient having an autonomous or independent life²².

Diseases that produce the cognitive deterioration and behavioural symptoms that lead to dementia in their final stages include Alzheimer's, which is the most frequent cause; however, there are other related disorders, like the degeneration of frontal and temporal lobes (that initially produces behavioural or language symptoms) or Lewy body dementia (that affects the frontal cortex causing cognitive, behavioural and motor symptoms)²².

Alzheimer's is responsible for 60-80% of dementia cases¹²². It initially presents as everyday, persistent forgetfulness of recently learned things, in addition to subtle problems related to language or thought²². Progression may occur at different speeds²³ until reaching a stage of dementia that causes increasing difficulties for independent living, may result in confusion, agitation, changes in personality and character, difficulties in recognising family members, incontinence and, during the most severe stages, difficulties in moving or swallowing and the need for continuous care²².

· [Central nervous system](#): the part of the nervous system composed of the brain and spinal cord.

· [Prions](#): a misfolded infectious protein that induces others of its type to adopt abnormal structures and extend the infection.

Parkinson's disease

Parkinson's is the second most common neurodegenerative disorder, with a significant number of undetected cases²⁴; estimations place the number of patients in Spain between 150,000 and 300,000²⁵⁻²⁷. There are double the number of cases in men, who also experience an earlier onset, than in women^{1,3,26}. Although prevalence increases from the age of 70²⁵, 25% of patients are younger than 65, and 5-10% are under the age of 50³.

There are various types of Parkinson's, and its presentations are heterogeneous but, in general, it is characterised by a combination of resting tremor, slowness of movement, reduced facial expressions and muscle rigidity that are initially limited to one part of the body²⁹. Among the first symptoms, particularly in more elderly patients, there may be other disorders, such as constipation, loss of smell, restless sleep, apathy or depression³⁰. Although the speed at which the disease develops varies in each person, and treatments can improve the symptoms, the progression of this disorder over decades make it a chronic process affecting multiple systems³¹. It can result in speech problems, postural instability and gait dysfunctions, sleep disorders and ultimately cognitive disorders and dementia, with other complications related to the patient's ageing process itself³².

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS)

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is the third most common of this type of disease, after dementias and Parkinson's, with 1.71-1.89 cases per 100,000 people in Europe and North America³³ and a prevalence in Spain of 6.1 cases per 100,000 inhabitants³⁴. Calculations for Spain estimate that 900 new cases are diagnosed each year³⁵. Given the low life expectancy, figures for ALS patients are not as high as those for other diseases, but it is calculated that between 4,000 and 4,500 people live with this disease³⁵. Although there are cases among young people, on average it presents at 65 years³⁴ and more frequently in men^{33,36}. The disease is characterised by progressive muscular weakness that can result in paralysis, affecting limbs, swallowing, the ability to cough, communication and breathing, although the senses and eye muscles function normally³⁷.

It can also cause cognitive deterioration and dementia in some patients³⁸. Most patients die between 3 to 5 years after the onset of symptoms due to respiratory failure, although 10-20% of patients survive more than 10 years³⁹.

Huntington's disease

Another of the most prevalent serious neurodegenerative diseases is Huntington's. In Canada and other populations of European ancestry its prevalence is around 12 people per 100,000⁴⁰⁻⁴². Although there are no studies for Spain, it is estimated that over 4,000 people are affected and 15,000 people are at risk of having inherited the mutation from a parent^{43,44}. Onset usually occurs between 30 and 50 years of age, with unspecific, heterogeneous symptoms such as feeling clumsier or being more irritable⁴⁵. Progression is inexorable⁴⁶, with a development over time of motor, cognitive and psychiatric symptoms, involuntary or imprecise movements (chorea), problems with planning and concentration, and behavioural changes that can result in frustration, apathy, depression and rage⁴⁷. More care is required at advanced stages and new symptoms may appear, such as rigidity, difficulty swallowing, weight loss, difficulty in communication and dementia⁴⁵.

Multiple sclerosis

Although multiple sclerosis has its origin in the dysregulation of some immune system cell types, it also induces neurodegeneration, which is the reason it is included in the Neurodegenerative Diseases Strategy and in this report¹.

The average age of onset for this disease is 32 years and it affects twice as many women as men^{48,49}. In Spain, over 58,000 people have the disease, with a prevalence of 123 patients per 100,000 inhabitants⁴⁹. It is known as the disease of a thousand faces due to its heterogeneity of symptoms and progress, although some of the most representative manifestations are problems of sight, loss of strength in limbs or half of the body, pins and needles, difficulty walking, dizziness, lack of coordination, problems controlling sphincters and fatigue⁵⁰.

Pathology: what happens to the neurons of diseased people.

In all of these disorders, different dysfunctions occur at cellular level that are still the subject of research (see Key point 2).

Huntington's disease

Has its origin in the mutation of a single gene, huntingtin⁵¹. If a person inherits a copy of the mutated gene from one of their parents, the disease is always triggered. The mutation generates a pathological protein that is longer than normal, where a single amino acid is repeated a minimum 36 times⁴⁶. This mutant protein cannot achieve the usual structure, and aggregates, which causes the death of **striatum** neurons, and later atrophies other regions of the brain⁴⁶. The children of parents with this disorder have a 50% probability of developing the disease, regardless of their sex⁴⁰.

Parkinson's disease

One of the proteins involved is alpha-synuclein (see Key point 2), which forms aggregates alongside other proteins (Lewy bodies) causing toxicity and cell death, particularly in the substantia nigra neurons that produce **dopamine**²⁸. Low levels of this neurotransmitter can cause problems in synaptic transmission and a disconnection between the brain and other parts of the body, which causes loss of movement control and other difficulties. The spread of this disease to other regions of the brain is associated with other symptoms, including dementia^{22,52}.

Alzheimer's disease

To date, the most commonly accepted mechanism explaining **Alzheimer's** is the amyloid hypothesis⁵³, which postulates the disease is triggered by aggregates of beta-amyloid protein⁵⁴ (see Key point 2). Outside the neurons, aggregates disrupt the neural connections, forming damaged structures of a larger size, such as fibrils and ultimately, plaques⁵³. In an attempt to clean the plaques and remains of dead neurons, immune cells congregate around the affected neurons, liberating inflammatory substances that may contribute to loss of **synapsis**⁵³ and establishing chronic inflammation²². A later event is the tangle aggregation of another misfolded protein, Tau, inside neurons⁵³. Although neuronal loss of Alzheimer's first affects regions involved in memory, like the hippocampus, it goes on to affect the neocortex, which is responsible for language, reasoning and social behaviour. Later, the damage spreads to other areas, causing the brain to shrink⁵⁵.

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis

The causes of ALS are still being researched. To date, scientists have observed the aggregation of different proteins, among which are TDP-43 and SOD1, which can spread damage from one cell to another^{7,56}. These mainly damage motor neurons, but also affect other nervous system cells⁷.

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- **Striatum**: The part of the brain that regulates, among others, voluntary movements and coordination of some aspects of behaviour.
 - **Dopamine**: Key neurotransmitter in motor function.
 - **Synapsis**: Neural structure that allows transmission of the nerve signal between neurons.

With the exception of multiple sclerosis, the neurodegenerative diseases in this report originate in dysfunctional proteins that accumulate, causing diverse problems of toxicity and death in neurons of the nervous system.

It is often complicated to understand which dysfunctions influence a disease's mechanism, and which arise first.

Multiple sclerosis

This is a disease of the central nervous system mediated by aberrant activation of the immune system: white blood cells enter the brain, inducing an inflammatory cascade that results in the loss of **myelin** and damage, with neural cell death that increases over the years⁵⁷. The result is scarring (sclerotic plaques) and problems in transmitting nerve impulses⁵⁸.

The connection with ageing, the processes that lead to neurodegeneration, or the role of the microbiota are some of the research topics common to all neurodegenerative diseases.

Key point 2. Cutting edge research

Ageing represents the biggest risk of the factors common to all neurodegenerative diseases. Researchers are attempting to make it possible to modify this factor, which has so far been inexorable, by means of cellular rejuvenation^{31,59,60}. Along these lines, investigators are currently exploring the possibility of biochemically reprogramming neurons to erase the marks of the past and rejuvenate them⁶¹.

In addition, neurodegeneration follows convergent paths in different diseases and such overlaps have also attracted scientific interest⁶².

On the other hand, Spain's State Reference Centres undertake research into health and social welfare, knowledge and information management, preparation of guidelines, dissemination of good practices and professional training nationally⁶³.

For subjects specific to each disease, part of the Alzheimer's research community proposes alternatives to the amyloid hypothesis⁵⁴. As an extension of the amyloid hypothesis, some scientists indicate that tau deposits cause more damage than the amyloid itself and highlight the advisability of combating both⁵⁴. Others suggest focussing on the inflammation and the processes that induce neural death⁶⁴, which are more active at later stages of the disease. Meanwhile, a minority theory points to microorganisms as trigger agents of amyloid accumulation: this postulates that the amyloid has antimicrobial functions and would aggregate to trap virus or bacteria⁵⁴.

Other scientists defend the stance that amyloid plaques and tau tangles are harmful and accelerate the disease, but rather than being the cause are one of the consequences of a pathological cascade that begins with an imbalance in cellular metabolism of cholesterol⁶⁵.

In Parkinson's, some researchers also question whether aggregation of the alpha-synuclein protein is the cause or consequence of neurodegeneration⁶⁶. Another major subject is research into inflammation in the process⁶⁶, and approaches with gene therapy to introduce a growth factor into the brain that can restore neural connectivity³¹.

In addition to a vaccine against the Epstein Barr virus, research in the field of multiple sclerosis is looking into how to achieve the remyelination of damaged areas, and the role of intestinal microbiota⁶⁷⁻⁷⁰, a topic that is also of interest in Parkinson's and Alzheimer's⁷¹⁻⁷³.

As Huntington's disease is caused by defects in a single gene, one of the main strategies against this disease is aimed at counteracting the expression of the mutant gene with short chains of nucleotides that specifically block production of the protein⁷⁴. Various therapies are already the subject of clinical trials, one of the most notable involves small molecules capable of crossing the blood-brain barrier; these molecules process the gene incorrectly before translation to protein, causing its degradation⁷⁴.

In ALS, the genetics of Spanish patients are being extensively characterised^{75,76} and antibodies against abnormal mutant proteins are being tested. Likewise, work is underway in the development of strategies based on gene therapy for the most frequent mutations³³. Another avenue of research is the role of skeletal muscle in the onset of this disease, as damage could be a primary event involved in the degeneration of motor neurons⁷⁷.

· **Myelin:** The insulating layer (sheath) that protects the extensions of nerve cells enabling the quick transmission of nerve impulses.

Causes and risk factors

Most cases are classified as sporadic, with causes derived from four relevant factors: genetics, environment, lifestyle and their interaction over time. Conversely, in a small percentage of cases, classified as familial origin, specific genetic variants are responsible for the disease.

Except for Huntington's, caused by mutations in a single gene, the genetic causes of neurodegenerative diseases are complex, and not fully understood.

For sporadic cases, genetics only represents a small percentage of the risk of developing the disease.

In most cases, which are sporadic, the causes of neurodegenerative disease are a cocktail of four important factors: genetics, environment, lifestyle and the interaction of these factors over time^{3,33,78}. Whereas the genetic component is to a large extent stable, environment and lifestyle are continuously changing. Due to this and to the difficulty in accessing the brain, it is currently difficult to determine the potentially causal or protective environmental factors that had an effect at a given time, or which accumulated over the years, interacting with each person's genetics³. The following sections review the current state of knowledge about the role of these variables in the risk of developing neurodegenerative diseases.

Although most cases are sporadic, for some diseases, such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's or ALS, specific genetic variants are responsible for a small percentage of cases, classified as familial origin, which affect younger people.

Genetic factors

Except for Huntington's, which is caused by mutations in a single gene, the genetic causes of neurodegenerative diseases are complex, and not fully understood⁵¹.

Alzheimer's disease

Currently, there are 75 genes known to influence the risk of suffering sporadic Alzheimer's and other related dementias, although they do not necessarily mean that the disease will develop⁷⁸. Among the variants, the most important is in gene *APOE E4*, which is not expressed in neurons but in other cells of the nervous system; it multiplies the risk of developing the disease between 3 and 12 times^{22,79,80}.

Familial Alzheimer's is passed from parents to children, generates memory problems, earlier onset dementia^{81,82} and has a different genetic origin that usually directly affects nerve cells⁸³. Although less than 1% of patients suffer familial Alzheimer's, one of the largest affected populations is in Colombia⁸¹. Studies of this population helped find two protective genetic combinations that delay the onset of the disease up to 20 years in people who carry the abnormal mutations^{82,84}. Research hopes to find new genetic variants that confer resilience to cognitive decline and dementia, developing treatments that also enable transfer of this protection to people affected by sporadic Alzheimer's⁸⁵.

Parkinson's disease

There are 90 known genetic variants that only explain 16–36% of the risk of suffering sporadic Parkinson's, which gives a clear indication of the knowledge gap about the causes of this disease⁸⁶. On the other hand, mutations in a handful of genes are directly responsible for familial Parkinson's, which only account for 3–5% of all cases^{3,87–90}. These hereditary mutations mean an early onset of symptoms, typically among people under the age of 40 years³.

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis

It is believed that cases of familial ALS only account for 10–20% of the total, so the majority of patients have no family history of this disease³³. We know that there are more than 40 genes that can induce familial ALS, and that they also play a role as risk factors in sporadic forms of this disease³³.

Multiple sclerosis

The weight of genetics in the risk of developing multiple sclerosis is 25%⁹¹. Currently, there are 236 variants identified as increasing the risk of suffering multiple sclerosis. Although none of them is sufficient, or necessary, to cause the disease, all of them contribute to the risk of developing it⁹². In addition, a new genetic variant has been identified that is associated with the most severe forms of the disease⁹³.

Environmental factors

Certain environmental and lifestyle factors are associated with variations in the risk of developing neurodegenerative diseases.

Although evaluating the weight of environmental factors and their interaction with the genetics of each patient is complicated and still requires further study³, certain environmental and lifestyle factors are associated with a reduced risk of developing these diseases. Conversely, the main non-modifiable risk factor is age, although neurodegenerative diseases are not a normal consequence of ageing⁶⁰.

Timely intervention in these factors could lead to fewer cases.

Alzheimer's disease and other dementias

Lesions characteristic of Alzheimer's begin to develop in the brain some 20 years before the onset of symptoms⁹⁴, which offers a window of opportunity to influence the course of the disease and delay its onset²².

An international commission of experts in dementia prevention, intervention and care identified 12 potential modifiable factors to which 40% of risk is attributable²². The ones that have the largest body of scientific evidence are (in parenthesis, percentage of reduction in the prevalence of dementia if this factor is eliminated): lower educational attainment at early stages of life (7%), loss of hearing (8%), traumatic brain injuries (3%), high blood pressure (2%), obesity (1%) or excessive alcohol consumption in middle-aged people (1%), smoking (5%), suffering from depression (4%), social isolation (4%), diabetes (1%) physical inactivity (2%) or being exposed to air pollution 96 at later stages of life (2%)⁹⁵.

These associations do not imply **causality** and some experts indicate that changes in lifestyle do not always bring the expected results⁹⁷. Nevertheless, other intervention studies have had successful outcomes⁹⁸ and are being repeated in different countries around the world⁹⁹. Moreover, the incidence of dementia seems to have decreased in richer countries in recent years, which is attributed to higher educational attainment and better control of cardiovascular risk^{22,95}. This evidence suggests that some of the variables identified may be the cause of dementia rather than just an association⁹⁵.

Experts indicate that, although further research is necessary, addressing the lifestyle factors associated with dementia and not delaying recommendations are positive steps that also bring benefits for other areas of health⁹⁵. They also highlight the need to implement specific programmes with concrete instructions about diet, physical and mental exercise, both to increase adherence to recommendations and so that the patient knows how to put them into practice. They also note the importance of controlling high blood pressure during intermediate stages of life.

In this sense, a simulation model estimates that modifying habits related with cardiovascular factors could lead to a 9% reduction of the prevalence of dementia in Spain, which would translate into 100,000 fewer cases and savings of 4,900 million euros by 2050¹⁰⁰.

· **Causality**: The possibility of establishing a cause-effect relationship between a risk factor and development of a disease.

Parkinson's disease

For Parkinson's, the association with the greatest weight, which has even served to establish animal models of the disease¹⁰¹, is exposure to environmental pollutants⁹⁶ such as the herbicide paraquat, the pesticide rotenone, or trichloroethylene, which is used to clean metals^{3,30}. Additionally, the unintentional consumption of the neurotoxin MPTP, produced accidentally during the clandestine synthesis of opioids, was found to be the direct, sudden cause of substantia nigra lesions that mimic Parkinson's disease^{29,102}. Conversely, smoking seems to be a protective factor against the disease^{28,103} and is associated with a later onset of symptoms¹⁰⁴. At the same time, tobacco consumption correlates with greater severity of some symptoms that are also associated with age and the long progression of Parkinson's¹⁰⁵. On the other hand, drug-induced parkinsonism, caused by some antipsychotics, antidepressants or [prokinetic agents](#), is reversible when medication is suspended¹⁰⁶. According to experts, there would be savings in specialist resources if the situation were detected in primary care. Finally, it is important to note that Parkinson's has also been associated with traumatic brain injury^{3,107,108}.

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis

The consumption of tobacco can double the risk of developing ALS compared to non-smokers¹⁰⁹⁻¹¹². There is also contradictory evidence: some studies indicate extenuating physical activity¹¹³ and cholesterol in blood as risk factors¹⁰⁹ in addition to pollutants³³.

Huntington's disease

In the case of a known family history of this disease, the only way to avoid it is by selecting embryos that do not carry the mutation^{114,115}.

Multiple sclerosis

In 2022, a study monitoring over 10 million soldiers in the American forces over a 20-year period detected that infection by the Epstein-Barr virus, the cause of infectious mononucleosis, gave a risk of developing multiple sclerosis that was 32 times higher¹¹⁶. Although infection by this virus is very common in the general population and not a cause of major problems, its presence may be necessary to trigger multiple sclerosis in people with a genetic predisposition¹¹⁷. Two vaccines are currently being worked on^{118,119} but experts believe we need a better understanding of how the infection triggers the disease. Other factors that seem to increase the risk of multiple sclerosis are a deficit of vitamin D, smoking or juvenile obesity^{120,121}. On the other hand, a higher level of educational attainment seems to be a protective factor⁹³.

Diagnosis

Patients of neurodegenerative diseases rarely receive an early diagnosis. Although diagnosis can be a serious setback for the patient and their family, it also opens the door to many medical and social advantages.

Infradiagnosis

Patients of neurodegenerative diseases do not often receive an early diagnosis.

It is estimated that 75% of dementia sufferers worldwide have not received a diagnosis¹²², due to a lack of awareness about this syndrome, or to social stigma, a lack of specialists or healthcare resources^{123,124} among other reasons. A study of the Spanish population found that only 30% of people with dementia had previously been diagnosed by healthcare services¹²⁵. Although these data are old, the Spanish Society of Neurology estimates that currently, over 50% of mild cases remain undiagnosed¹²⁶, a figure that could be as high as 90%¹⁰. Other studies find that, at the time of diagnosis, most patients are already at a moderate stage of dementia¹⁰ but the medical community notes that this aspect has improved in recent years.

·[Prokinetic agents](#): Drugs that interfere with receptors of dopamine or serotonin which are used to improve bowel transit because they stimulate the contraction of smooth muscle.

It is often difficult to detect ALS at an early stage since the onset can be confused with other, more common, diseases, which means that patients are not referred to a neurologist³³. Something similar occurs with Parkinson's because current diagnosis is based on clinical assessment, which highlights the importance of evaluation by a specialist³. Although medical professionals indicate that the situation in Spain is better, a survey in the United Kingdom found that 26% of Parkinson's patients had received a misdiagnosis¹²⁷.

Although receiving the diagnosis of a neurodegenerative disease for which there is currently no cure represents a serious setback for the patient and their family¹²², neurologists highlight the advantages of early diagnosis. One of the main benefits is access to effective treatments that can improve symptoms and to non-pharmacological interventions or, in the case of multiple sclerosis, being able to hold back the disease (**see the section on Treatment**). Treatments are more effective if they are applied at the best time during the disease's progression^{121,128}. Diagnosis also provides a patient with answers, avoids extra visits and can help with a better prognosis of the disease's course. For instance, the mild cognitive deterioration caused by some psychoactive drugs, vascular problems etc. (not in the case of Alzheimer's) can be halted or reversed^{122,129}. Diagnosis of these disorders before they lead to dementia can save costs in healthcare and long-term care which are calculated at 7 billion dollars for the USA²². Diagnosis also opens the door to participation in clinical trials offering new therapeutic opportunities and a more effective evaluation of treatments¹³⁰. It also enables long-term organisation of care and legal preparation for when patients reach the most advanced stages of the disease¹²².

Diagnostic methods

The exploration and judgment of the medical specialist can be complemented in the case of Alzheimer's, Huntington's disease, and multiple sclerosis with diagnostic tests not yet available for Parkinson's disease and ALS. The diagnosis of the latter two also relies on complementary tests.

In order to detect cognitive deterioration, a full medical history and neuropsychological evaluation are conducted; this includes tests of memory, attention, orientation, language and problem solving¹³¹. These tests help detect cognitive deterioration and behavioural alterations in an objective way, can indicate which regions of the brain are more involved, and suggest a cause¹³¹. The work of a neurophysiologist is also essential alongside that of other professionals to design a personal care plan¹³².

Diagnosing the cause of cognitive deterioration requires a very detailed study. Some complementary tests, such as blood tests or neuroimaging help rule out secondary or potentially treatable causes of cognitive deterioration (B12 deficiency, tumours, vascular lesions, infectious diseases, etc. that are also the cause of cognitive deterioration)¹²³. Likewise, neuroimaging can inform about patterns of brain atrophy and suggest the origin of the cognitive symptoms¹³³.

If the suspected cause of cognitive deterioration is **Alzheimer's**, it can be diagnosed after a medical examination with lumbar puncture to extract cerebrospinal fluid and analyse various biomarkers that are signs of the disease's presence in the brain^{134,135}. This technique is simple, cheap and causes very few side effects but requires specialist personnel and organisation^{123,133}. Another option is positron emission tomography (amyloid PET) a non-invasive technique that also provides an effective diagnosis¹³³ although it is a more expensive test¹²³.

The prognosis of **Parkinson's** and **ALS** is clinical but corroborated with complementary tests^{3,33,138}.

For **Huntington's** disease, diagnosis consists of genetic testing to check for the presence of abnormal mutant variants in the patient's DNA.

In **multiple sclerosis** there is a need for clinical diagnosis and tests that enable other conditions with similar symptoms to be ruled out. One of the tests that helps in this process is cerebrospinal fluid testing, which detects markers of underlying inflammation^{139,140}. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is another, more sensitive, technique to identify lesions that are characteristic of the disease, which offers information about its possible development^{48,139}. Early diagnosis is key to start anti-inflammatory therapies as soon as possible and avoid the disability derived from neural damage¹²¹.

The future of diagnosis

Expectations are that diagnosis of Alzheimer's will be possible with a simple blood test.

A new technique promises effective early detection of Parkinson's from samples of cerebrospinal fluid.

Analysis of Alzheimer's biomarkers in blood is minimally invasive, accessible, scalable and cheap, is already successfully used in research, and envisioned to reach clinical practice in the near future¹²³. It does, however, require more sensitive testing since concentrations of biomarkers in blood are lower than in cerebrospinal fluid¹⁴¹. There are currently several valid biomarkers in blood to distinguish Alzheimer's from other neurodegenerative diseases¹⁴²⁻¹⁴⁴. A negative result could rule out Alzheimer's and avoid the patient undergoing other diagnostic tests, such as lumbar puncture¹²³. In future, it is hoped that blood tests will be enough to diagnose Alzheimer's and follow-up the disease. Even so, experts indicate that more clinical practice experience with more heterogeneous populations is still necessary, as is standardisation of measurements to ensure transfer and reproducibility in different laboratories¹²³.

It is possible to detect biomarkers in blood even before cognitive symptoms appear. So, this type of testing is a useful tool to select participants in clinical trials. In this context, although detection at an early stage does not imply that the disease will develop¹³⁰ it is necessary to inform the patient of the significance of knowing the results of testing¹²³.

For Parkinson's, a recently published study reported detection of alpha-synuclein aggregates in cerebrospinal fluid with 88% effectiveness for diagnosis at early stages, even before motor symptoms present¹⁴⁵. Work is also underway on diagnosis using blood samples in this and other diseases^{146,147}.

Support after diagnosis

Both patients and their carers need counselling from diagnosis to help manage the negative feelings it triggers, combat barriers such as discrimination or stigma, and obtain resources to cope with the disease.

Both patients and their families may experience anticipatory grief from the time of diagnosis, with feelings of uncertainty and loss of hopes and dreams for the future¹²².

To better cope with the disease and combat these feelings of shock, desperation, powerlessness, frustration, fear and anxiety, neurodegenerative disease patients need professional support from the moment of diagnosis¹²². In the case of ALS, understanding the disease and expediting processes is particularly important because of its rapid progression to disability¹⁴⁸. ALS patients therefore call for the accreditation of dedicated units so that diagnosis comes with automatic recognition of a 33% degree of disability¹⁴⁹.

In Alzheimer's and other related diseases, support after diagnosis promotes personal autonomy, and delays access to long-term care¹⁵⁰ (**see Key point 3**). In Spain, the majority of dementia patient carers who answered a survey stated that they had received very limited or no information about key aspects of the disease and have very little knowledge about the healthcare and social welfare resources available^{10,151}. Based on this situation, one of the objectives of the National Plan on Alzheimer's and other dementias¹⁰ is to inform, train and provide counselling after diagnosis.

Key point 3. Support after diagnosis of dementia in other countries.

Different countries adopt different approaches to post-diagnosis support. In South Korea, there is a network of local centres that combine aspects of healthcare and social welfare. This strategy has increased the number of people with dementia who continue to live in their communities and reduced the medical costs of long-term care¹²².

The Scottish model (United Kingdom) is considered the best example of post-diagnostic support in the world and has helped thousands of patients since 2013¹²². Patients recently diagnosed with dementia receive support for at least one year from a case manager called a *link worker* who has training in this disease^{122,125}. With a person-based approach, the link worker serves to guide patients and their families through this disease: helping them understand the dementia, manage symptoms and increase resilience to maintain independence for as long as possible¹⁵². The worker also connects patients with the services they need, helps plan care, and provides advice on making informed legal decisions, ensuring that the services have the patient's consent¹⁵². The link worker also connects patients with other people with dementia who collaborate so that the patient can maintain their social network and obtain support to keep participating in activities they enjoy¹⁵².

As Huntington's disease is hereditary, it generates anxiety in families because the descendants, who may have seen the disease in one of their parents, have a 50% probability of also developing it in the future. In this sense, they can benefit from psychological support to prepare themselves, decide whether to undergo genetic testing, and help in dealing with the diagnosis¹⁵³.

People who receive a diagnosis when they are young adults, as is the case of multiple sclerosis, or a get a positive result in genetic testing for Huntington's disease, face their own challenges. For instance, a study of people who had tested positive for Huntington's but were still asymptomatic found that many of them became more aware of the passing of time and speeded up their life events; it also influenced their thoughts about having children or not¹⁵⁴. They also indicated the challenge represented by revealing their genetic status to potential partners or in the work environment, for fear of discrimination¹⁵⁴. For instance, research undertaken in the 2000s found that women who received a diagnosis of multiple sclerosis were 6 times more likely to divorce or separate than male patients¹⁵⁵. Patients also face multiple barriers at work, and it is more likely that they will require adjustments to carry out their functions¹⁵⁶. Indeed, it has been found that the numbers of people with multiple sclerosis who are employed is 20% less than the general population and that the disease affects the productivity of 72% of those who have a job¹⁵⁷. Invisible symptoms such as fatigue, cognitive difficulties or mood disorders can have a great impact on the capacity to work¹⁵⁷.

Treatment

To date, neurodegenerative diseases have no cure. However, treatments exist that can hold back multiple sclerosis or control the most incapacitating symptoms of Parkinson's.

To date, there are no cures for neurodegenerative diseases. However, treatments exist that can hold back multiple sclerosis¹²¹ or control the most incapacitating symptoms of Parkinson's disease³. In different conditions, many of the symptoms, which vary over the years, can be treated with drugs or specific interventions¹.

Medical and pharmacological interventions

Parkinson's disease

When symptoms begin to make the activities of daily living difficult, the most effective, best-tolerated first-line treatment is levodopa, alongside other drugs such as [dopamine antagonists](#)^{3,158}. Levodopa contributes to restoring correct levels of dopamine and improves tremors, muscle rigidity and slowness of movement¹⁵⁹. Although patients fear this medicine will accelerate the progression of Parkinson's, there is no evidence that it changes the course of the disease¹⁶⁰. For some patients it can cause an increase in involuntary movements^{161,162}, but their frequency and severity have reduced in recent years thanks to better dose control¹⁶².

· [Dopamine antagonists](#): Drug that limits the effects of dopamine in the brain.

All neurodegenerative diseases have treatments to alleviate symptoms, with varying degrees of efficacy. Except for multiple sclerosis, the other conditions do not have treatments that significantly slow down the progression of the disease.

Levodopa can be combined with other medications and, as a second line, use sustained-release devices¹⁶². This maintains stable levels of the substance, which are more similar to the physiological ones, avoiding the oscillations in dopamine levels derived from metabolism of the drug, which may be responsible for the adverse effects¹⁶².

Over the years, the deficit of dopamine increases due to nerve cell degeneration, and medication may not be sufficient to cover it. In that case, the patient can be treated with deep brain stimulation¹⁶³. This consists of the placement of a programmable device to block the neural activity of specific problematic areas of the brain using continuous high-frequency electrical currents¹⁶⁴. Although surgery has risks, this procedure reduces the symptoms that respond to levodopa in patients with advanced Parkinson's for several years, as well as eliminating or reducing the adverse effects derived from pharmacological treatments^{165,166}.

On the other hand, a new, non-invasive treatment called high-intensity focused ultrasound (HIFU) can reduce the main signs (slowness of movement, resting tremor, rigidity) immediately and without the complications of a surgery^{167,168}. Its mechanism of action is based on ultrasound, which precisely eliminates the areas responsible for the motor signs using heat¹⁶⁷. A recent study suggests that its application may be beneficial at early stages¹⁶⁹.

Alzheimer's disease and other dementias

Following the success of restoring dopamine levels in Parkinson's, attempts are being made to recover the normal activity of certain neurotransmitters in the symptomatic treatment of Alzheimer's or Lewy bodies diseases¹²². Although they are not as effective as their equivalents in Parkinson's, and have side effects to consider, these medicines have proved effective in numerous clinical trials and the patients, their families and physicians perceive benefits from their use¹²².

However, some professionals are questioning the use of psychopharmaceuticals to treat neuropsychiatric symptoms such as agitation, aggression or psychosis in patients with Alzheimer's or other dementias¹²². There is no conclusive evidence for the effectiveness of all the drugs in use to treat dementias and only some of them have modest benefits for certain symptoms in a small percentage of patients¹⁷⁰⁻¹⁷³. Along the same lines, some studies find a 1.8 times higher risk of mortality and other adverse effects associated with this type of drug¹⁷⁰⁻¹⁷³, highlighting the need to consider risks versus benefits when prescribing them, and proposing that this should occur on a case by case basis¹²². The Spanish Society of Geriatrics and Gerontology has also requested the legal prohibition of chemical restraint, i.e., the non-therapeutic use of psychopharmaceuticals in order to restrict mobility or control behaviour for reasons of organisational convenience rather than for a patient's benefit¹⁷⁴.

In the last 20 years, there have been no new drugs to alleviate the symptoms of Alzheimer's or other types of cognitive deterioration¹²², but the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has just approved the first drug that can modify Alzheimer's disease⁹⁰. In the EU, the European Medicines Agency could authorise its use in the near future, although its cost-benefit ratio is still under discussion^{137,175}. After the failure of other medications, and although it is far from being a cure, this new drug is considered a major step forward¹³⁷. It is an antibody that, for the first time, has managed to reduce amyloid plaques and cognitive deterioration in 25% of patients with early stages of the disease¹⁷⁶. Estimates are that it delays progression of the disease some 6 months¹³⁷ although the pharmaceutical company's projections estimate a delay of up to 3 years, which it has not yet been possible to prove¹⁷⁷.

Some estimates calculate that 5.4 million patients in the 27 countries of the EU could be eligible to use this medication¹³⁷. If its price, which has not yet been fixed, were similar to that of the United States, treating all of the possible patients would cost the equivalent of half of the total EU spending on pharmaceuticals, which experts consider to be exorbitant¹³⁷. In addition to this expense, we would have to add the cost of adapting the healthcare system to diagnose Alzheimer's, periodic administration of the drug and monitoring of the first phases of treatment^{137,178}. On the other hand, we need to consider that delaying the disability of patients is a saving, since the social costs of care can be three times the costs of healthcare¹⁷⁹. Another issue to consider is that estimates applying clinical trial inclusion criteria calculate an eligibility for these emerging treatments which is very much lower than the 5.4 million patients mentioned above¹⁸⁰. Finally, there is another antibody that has offered very promising results in new clinical trials¹⁸¹.

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis

There is only one drug that holds back the progression of ALS, which was approved in the mid-1990s and gives some extra months of life for certain groups of patients^{33,182}. Nevertheless, evidence indicates that it only prolongs life at more advanced stages of the disease when the patient has a lower quality of life¹⁸³. According to medical professionals, its all-round contribution is poor and the short-term prognosis for this disease is fatal for the majority of patients.

Patients can also receive treatments for symptoms such as excessive salivation or muscle rigidity, in addition to other medical interventions such as non-invasive ventilation and gastrostomy to improve nutrition³³.

Huntington's disease

There is currently no treatment that modifies the course of this disease⁷⁴. Despite the hopes of patients, a phase III clinical trial whose target was to reduce the amount of pathological protein, was cancelled some years ago due to the drug's lack of effectiveness^{184,185}. Recently, however, a review of the data has reopened the trial with younger patients¹⁸⁵.

There are drugs to treat **chorea** which also improve other motor and psychiatric aspects, although some of these therapies may exacerbate depression and suicidal thoughts¹⁸⁶. A new drug to improve chorea has shown good results in a phase III clinical trial¹⁸⁷.

Multiple sclerosis

Effective treatments for multiple sclerosis have increased over the last two decades¹²¹. Although not all patients respond, various treatments are able to modify the course of the disease, which in some cases can stop flare-ups, hold up progression of the disease and avoid the appearance of new active lesions¹⁸⁸. One of the most effective, safe and tolerable are antibodies against **B cells**, which appear to be dysfunctional and pro-inflammatory in these patients^{121,189}. So, due to their good benefit risk ratio, there has been a transition from escalating these treatments step by step to, in many cases, prioritising high effectiveness from the start, preventing inflammation reaching the central nervous system and triggering neurodegeneration¹²¹.

Although the disease is the same, progressive forms of multiple sclerosis (without flare-ups) follow a different clinical course, with the same abnormal mutant characteristics and different degrees of expression, according to genetic or environmental determinants⁹¹. Despite advances, for these patients there is only one treatment that can hold back the disease, which is not always effective¹²¹. Meanwhile, several molecules that are able to simultaneously inhibit different immune cells and attack the disease on several fronts are being tested, which could also be a successful therapy for progressive forms¹⁹⁰.

· **Chorea**: The involuntary, uncoordinated movements that Huntington's disease causes.

· **B cells**: The white blood cells that produce antibodies.

There are also treatments for symptoms like muscular tension, fatigue, pain, sphincter control, cognitive deterioration and others¹⁸⁸.

Improving the transfer of research to practice

Between 2002 and 2012, 99.6% of the clinical trials testing new therapies for Alzheimer's failed^{6,191} and the situation was similar for other neurodegenerative diseases⁶. One of the reasons is that the animal models used in these contexts, such as mice, cannot fully reproduce the human disease so the results obtained are often not reproducible in patients⁶.

Although mice can be a good initial model, as they are manageable and their genetics are well known, some researchers propose using animals that are more similar to human beings, such as miniature pigs¹⁹² or non-human primates¹⁹³. Other suggestions include intermediate approaches, such as implanting human nerve cells in a mouse brain⁶⁴. Many recent studies use human cells that are genetically reprogrammed to differentiate them from neurons, which can also be cultured in three dimensions and form cerebral organoids. However, such models are still undergoing a standardisation optimisation process⁶.

To improve the results of translational research and achieve treatments that can modify the course of these diseases, the scientific community also highlights the need to discover new biomarkers or improve existing ones to track both the disease's progression and the effectiveness of drugs. Another improvement would be to personalise treatments, whether by means of cerebrospinal fluid or blood plasma analysis^{31,194,195}.

Focussing clinical trials on specific populations of patients, stratified by symptoms and according to the molecular subtype of the disease presented can also contribute to success as the heterogeneity of the sample decreases¹⁹⁵. Other approaches aim to increase the effectiveness and reduce the cost of clinical trials by testing several molecules at the same time¹⁹⁶.

Another consideration is that the blood-brain barrier is very selective and only allows certain substances to pass through so as to protect the brain from infections and other toxic agents. An important area of research into neurodegenerative diseases is how to cross the barrier, enabling treatments to access the brain and gain effectiveness^{197,198}.

Patients could also benefit from advances in neuroimaging methods, such as specific markers for positron emission tomography or structural and functional MRI that enable the *in vivo* study of a patient³¹.

With this panorama, experts point out the advisability of improving the capacity of Spain's science system to transfer knowledge on these and other diseases to the industrial sector and ensure returns that contribute to the system's sustainability.

Non-pharmacological interventions

As disease progresses, the situation of a patient worsens and new symptoms appear that require a comprehensive care approach¹²². As well as medication, most patients can benefit from one or several non-pharmacological interventions at some time during the course of their disease. These are defined as any intervention that is not based on medication, has a theoretical basis, is focussed and reproducible for a patient or the carer, and potentially capable of achieving relevant benefit¹⁹⁹.

To enhance the effectiveness of clinical trials testing drugs targeting neurodegenerative diseases, experts recommend using experimental models that better replicate human diseases, developing new biomarkers or improving existing ones, and reducing heterogeneity in participant samples.

Patients can improve their condition with interventions like taking exercise, better nutrition, physiotherapy, psychological care, speech and language therapy or occupational therapy.

For instance, there is evidence that aerobic exercise has positive cognitive effects and improves mental function in people with mild cognitive deterioration, Alzheimer's and different dementias^{122,200,201}. High-intensity aerobic exercise is safe for early Parkinson's patients and is expected to improve or even hold back both motor and non-motor symptoms^{31,202}. Studies also report improvements in the physical state and walking endurance of Huntington's patients²⁰³. And, although further long-term research is necessary, evidence seems to indicate that exercise is also beneficial for multiple sclerosis patients²⁰⁴.

There are different types of physiotherapy available for all of the diseases described in this report, to reduce rigidity, improve the quality of movement, postural control, stability, breathing, etc.^{24,43,188,199,205}.

Likewise, psychological attention is beneficial (in the case of dementias, it is more indicated at early and moderate stages), speech and language therapy if there are disorders of speech or swallowing, interventions to improve nutrition, and occupational therapy that can help patients and carers carry out activities of daily living, by modifying either the task or the environment^{24,122,188,199,205-207}.

Along the same lines, people with dementia who join in activities aimed at improving cognition experience varying degrees of progress (**see Key point 4**).

People with Alzheimer's and other related diseases experience improvement with therapies such as cognitive training, interventions using art, and group cognitive stimulation.

Group cognitive stimulation has very positive effects and is also cost effective.

Key point 4. Cognitive interventions

Cognitive training consists of the formal practice of skills and processes like memory, processing information, attention and executive functions by means of repeating increasingly difficult tasks¹²². There is evidence that people with moderate or mild dementia experience small or moderate cognitive improvement in the short and medium terms, above all, in semantic verbal fluency, language and short-term memory^{122,208,209}. Although further study is necessary, there is also an association between cognitive training and a delay in disease progression, as well as a reduction in the carer's burden when treatment ends²⁰⁸. However, there is no evidence that this improves quality of life, the functional capacity to perform activities of daily living or behaviour patterns, although it is known that there are no negative effects^{122,208,209}.

For their part, cognitive stimulation therapies consist in performing group activities with patients who have mild to moderate dementia in order to strengthen their memory, executive functions and language in addition to improving their wellbeing and avoiding psychiatric complications¹²². Among other activities, these include word or physical games, questions, categorising objects or talking about current affairs¹²². Although there is a demand for more rigorous studies²¹⁰ evidence indicates that this therapy improves cognition, quality of life, language and the social interaction of participants, and can even have more effect than some medicines²¹¹⁻²¹⁴. It seems that the benefit the group generates is important and it may be an advantage that the facilitator is not a family member^{122,215}. Calculations estimate that offering cognitive stimulation to all the dementia patients in England would be a cost-effective intervention^{122,216}.

Likewise, for people with dementia, interventions that use art (poetry, narrative, theatre, dance, painting, pottery and music) can help to reduce stress, anxiety, depression or behavioural disorders, as well as improving social and cognitive aspects^{122,217,218}. They can also be therapeutic for carers²¹⁹. Experts indicate that further studies should define certain parameters such as what is the key to the success of an intervention or how long the effects should last for a therapy to be considered beneficial^{122,220-222}.

Again, some studies indicate inequality of access to non-pharmacological therapies in Spain, and there are no data that report the number of patients who use them^{10,136}.

On the other hand, it is important that people with neurodegenerative diseases and their families have access to up-to-date, truthful information, and the resources to avoid disinformation or access to fraudulent therapies, which are financially burdensome and serve no purpose; this is a risk for patients' health and can delay access to effective treatments^{123,223-225}.

Attending a palliative care consultation at an early stage seems to improve the quality of life of neurodegenerative disease patients, although access to this service is not the same countrywide.

Palliative care

The goal of palliative care is to guarantee the quality of life of patients with a serious disease who face the physical, psychological, social or existential problems inherent to a potentially fatal disease^{226,227}. The focus here is on three dimensions: addressing the symptoms, environmental support, and planning treatment and care in accordance with the patient's preferences^{228,229}.

Early access to a palliative consultation reduces hospital admissions for dementia patients^{22,230} improves the quality of the care they receive in their last 14 days of life, reduces the possibility of them receiving pointless treatments or interventions^{122,231}; it also lowers the costs of the last month of life^{122,231}. Early access to palliative care is also considered beneficial for other neurodegenerative diseases. On one hand, it ensures that the care is person-centred, as it helps in drawing up a shared care plan and the possibility of preparing an advance healthcare directive (also called a living will)^{232,233}. On the other, treatments are personalised to control symptoms. This can include strategies for difficulties swallowing (changing textures in the diet or improving nutrition), problems with catheters such as deciding where to place or when to remove them, the need to begin mechanical ventilation, reduce dribbling or constipation, treat psychological and cognitive problems, combat pain, help with sleep and end-of-life assistance. This aspect also includes support for the carer and in the grieving process^{10,227,232,234,235}.

Only 10% of medical faculties and 48% of nursing faculties offer specific obligatory courses in palliative care that guarantee basic capacity building in these skills²³⁶. Neurologists note the need for more training and call for the creation of specific protocols for each condition to make health care more uniform^{237,238}.

In terms of access to palliative care, the European Association for Palliative Care recommends that there should be two palliative care services for every 100,000 inhabitants, one home-based and the other in-hospital²³⁶. However, Spain is at the bottom of the list of European countries, with 0.6 services for every 100,000 inhabitants²³⁶. Although some specialist units have palliative care professionals, for instance, some ALS units, this is not a common situation. Indeed, healthcare professionals indicate that for other neurodegenerative diseases palliative care is deficient²³⁷. Access to this service is unequal, with different resources and organisation in each autonomous community²³⁸. To improve the situation, the National Palliative Care Strategy was updated in 2011 and healthcare professionals want to promote a palliative care law that sets minimums to guarantee better equality of access^{239,240}.

Adaptation of the National Health System

To adapt to the foreseeable increase in the number of neurodegenerative disease cases, the medical community recommends more health and social welfare coordination, the creation of a patient registry, training for primary care staff, more specialist physicians and the creation of a professional role specialised in patients with dementia.

In light of the challenge presented by neurodegenerative diseases and a foreseeable increase in the number of cases, medical professionals highlight the need to undertake the following adaptations of the healthcare system:

Data and coordination of health and social welfare

To prepare a response to the increase in the number of cases of certain neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's and other dementias, it would be very useful to have a periodically updated accurate patient registry^{10,241} like the Dementias Platform UK or the Swedish registry for cognitive/dementia disorders¹⁰. According to the medical community, this information would help organise not only clinical trials but also enable more precise estimates of the drug requirements for medicines that can modify the course of diseases like Alzheimer's if approval is given¹⁰.

Likewise, experts mention the need to coordinate social services and healthcare to the benefit of patients and the effectiveness of the system^{10,242}. For instance, it would be advisable

to have data about social services categorised in greater detail about neurodegenerative diseases, such as how many of the people living in residential care facilities, or who need care, have dementia.

Distribution of resources

There are currently eight Reference Centres, Services and Units (Spanish acronym, CSUR) designated to perform surgery for movement disorders in the autonomous communities of Catalonia, Madrid, Valencia, Galicia, Basque Country and the Principality of Asturias²⁴³. There are also six reference centres for rare diseases that present movement disorders, which would include Huntington's disease, in the autonomous communities of Andalusia, Catalonia, Valencia and Madrid. The twelve CSUR for multiple sclerosis are located in Aragon, Catalonia, the communities of Madrid and Valencia, Galicia, the Region of Murcia and the Basque Country²⁴³. Neuromuscular diseases CSUR (in Andalusia, Catalonia, the autonomous communities of Madrid, Valencia and the Basque Country) treat ALS patients²⁴³ although the reference centres are not specifically for ALS, and medical professionals consider that at advanced stages these patients require care close to home.

The way that healthcare professionals are organised in hospitals is also important. For instance, the treatment of patients in multi-disciplinary units consisting of different specialists (medical and nursing professionals, case managers, psychologists, social workers, rehabilitation and palliative care staff) improves both the survival and quality of life of ALS patients, in addition to reducing the number of hospital admissions²⁴⁴⁻²⁴⁶.

On the other hand, medical professionals highlight the need to distribute resources and achieve sufficient regional cover, and the advisability of setting up permanent inter-hospital referral systems that make the whole process quicker both for users and for hospitals to recover funding¹.

Healthcare professionals

Experts recommend training in and improved awareness of neurodegenerative diseases for primary care professionals to facilitate early diagnosis and improve coordination with specialist services^{10,24}.

Within Spain, 18% of healthcare professionals believe that more neurologists are needed, and 67.3% think there is a lack of psychiatrists²⁴⁷. Another need is to expand access to rehabilitation programmes.

On the other hand, as dementias are so prevalent, it is increasingly common to find patients admitted to acute care hospitals, where they are at greater risk of suffering negative consequences²⁴⁸. To improve patient care and that of carers during hospital stays, the United Kingdom has created a specialist nursing corps, *Admiral Nurses*²⁴⁸. In addition to providing person-centred holistic care for the patient they provide support for families and also train other health and social welfare professionals to promote evidence-based best practices²⁴⁸.

Assistance and care

Social services face the challenge of adapting to the increasing number of people who will presumably need more complex care and are more vulnerable in critical situations, such as the recent pandemic.

The care of people with neurodegenerative disease mostly falls to the family, with the consequent social and personal cost. Forecasts indicate the need to develop a sustainable system of professional, specialised care.

Healthcare and social services face the challenge of adapting to the increasing number of people who will presumably need more complex care²⁴⁹ and are more vulnerable in critical situations, such as during the recent pandemic²⁵⁰.

There are three basic pillars in the healthcare of people with neurodegenerative diseases:

Carers

Forecasts predict the need to train carers and staff specialised in the looking after people with dementia and chronic diseases^{59,249}. However, in Spain, it is the family that mainly provides care for these patients.

Neurodegenerative diseases represent an economic burden for patients and their families. For instance, based on available data, in southern European countries, it is calculated that the cost of dementia is around 36,000 euros per year per patient²⁵¹, although other studies give the most conservative estimates as 42,336 euros²⁵². What is known is that cost of the social welfare component is higher than that of healthcare and increases with the severity and duration of the disease^{179,251,253}. Calculations are that 60% of the total cost of care corresponds to non-paid or informal care, usually provided by family members²⁵⁴, which could involve financial risk, only 30% of which is mitigated by the public protection system²⁵⁵. This is very important in terms of the population since, according to the INE (Spanish Statistical Office) Survey on Disability, Personal Autonomy and Dependency Situations, the number of people who receive informal care in their homes increased more than 40% between 2008 and 2021²⁵⁶. A preliminary study estimates that in Spain, the medical cost of substituting the informal care of Alzheimer's patients with professional carers could be as high as 70,000 euros per patient per year²⁵⁷.

Changes in work schedules (a reduction in working hours or leaving paid employment, since sometimes availability needs to be round-the-clock, every day of the year) in order to care for family members implies lower incomes for families, a difficulty in combining care with employment, and complications when it comes to re-joining the workforce for carers, who are mostly women, when the patient dies¹⁰. Social changes, such as smaller families, higher participation of women in the labour market or raising the age of retirement, reduce the availability of adult children for this type of task, which highlights the importance of developing a sustainable, professional, specialised care system²⁴⁹. For the time being, in addition to benefits and dependency services, one resource that helps keep potential carers in employment are adult day care centres, where patients can also receive therapeutic help^{10,59}.

Although caring for a family member can give a feeling of pride and a sense of purpose, it can also be a source of stress and other negative feelings, like loneliness and isolation, guilt or regret over decisions about the future of the sick relative^{122,258}. For instance, 54% of dementia patient carers state that they often or always feel under stress¹²². Others, particularly women, have health problems, difficulty enjoying leisure or problems related with their professional activity^{259,260}. As the burden increases in step with disease progress and the loss of patient autonomy, the costs of the carer losing their job²⁶¹ can lead to depression and a loss of quality of life²⁶². If these obstacles are not overcome, exhaustion of the carer often leads to the patient being admitted²⁶².

Social inclusion in the community is essential to empower Alzheimer's patients and other related diseases. This is fostered if they are considered when designing the environment and receive support from technological resources supervised by carers.

When people with Alzheimer's or other dementias can no longer live at home, alternatives include "coexistence units" and other options already firmly established in other European countries.

Associations representing ALS and Huntington's call for the creation of centres that specialise in their diseases.

Inclusion of Alzheimer's patients in the community

Social inclusion in the community is essential for the empowerment of people with Alzheimer's. This is made easier if the environment is designed with adaptations like good signage, accessibility, awareness and training of people who work in shops or services²⁶³. Access to outdoor areas is a right of people with dementia, and activities in natural surroundings increase the wellbeing of patients and their carers²⁶⁴. Gardens provide a multi-sensory experience with similar benefits, and they can be designed along similar lines as mentioned above, with the inclusion of areas to rest, shade, plants that feel pleasant to touch or that evoke the seasons, etc.²⁶⁵. One of the main pillars of Spain's National Plan on Alzheimer's is transformation of the environment by raising sensitivity to and awareness of the disease¹⁰.

In Spain and other countries, the aim is for older adults to receive support in their home environment enabling them to live as long as possible at home^{59,266}. There are objects that can help people stay at home with a good quality of life and the support of their carer. Such devices include the digital watch that also shows the date and day of the week, touch lamps to help prevent falls, whiteboards to write down the week's activities or reminders not to forget the house keys²⁶⁷. Technology can also come in the shape of care robots, geolocation devices, telehealth services, virtual therapies or communication tools, although their success depends on the patient's profile and access to the technology^{59,242}.

Alternative accommodation

Due to limitations in the design of conventional homes and the difficulty of finding specialised accommodation, despite support, many people with dementia cannot maintain an acceptable quality of life in their own homes when the disease reaches an advanced stage²⁶⁸.

When this occurs, one of the alternatives to traditional residential care facilities are what is known in Spain as a *unidad de convivencia* ("coexistence unit"). These are home-like places, with private and community areas, where a reduced number of people live, with continuous attention organised on a small scale^{59,269,270}. The pilot projects put into practice in Spain have met with high degrees of satisfaction from residents, professionals and families^{59,269}.

In the Netherlands, the *dementia village* project reproduces the areas of a small village (squares, streets, gardens, supermarket, restaurant) so that its inhabitants, 150 people with dementia, can participate in daily activities in freedom and safety²⁷⁰. Six or seven people live in each independent terraced house, grouped by preferences and interests, accompanied by permanent teams of professionals²⁷⁰. The success of this closed community project has meant that it has been copied in countries like France, Canada, Switzerland and Denmark²⁷⁰.

The United Kingdom has set up specialised *extra care housing* projects for older adults. These are similar to the community cohousing projects that already exist in Spain to promote the autonomy of older adults, where inhabitants live in independent apartments with access to shared utilities (laundry, restaurant, gym, hairdresser) and activities designed to liven up community living. They also offer residents the possibility of contracting the degree of care that adapts to their increasing needs over time^{59,268}. These alternatives also have the potential to improve a dementia patient's quality of life and cover their different needs as their condition changes. For instance, support for the dementia patient increases because living with their partner is possible, and the carer's quality of life improves because they gain social contacts and independence. Experts recommend thinking about the specific needs of people with cognitive deterioration when it comes to designing and managing this type of project²⁶⁸.

In the case of ALS patients, the rapid progression of this disease leads them to need continuous care, so they call for financial support for home care or a place in a specialist public residential care facility²⁷¹ where there are staff trained in specific care, such as cleaning tracheostomy tube components or reacting to emergency situations to prevent suffocation²⁷². There is currently only one such centre planned, and a day care centre in Madrid²⁷³. There are no specialist centres for other diseases such as Huntington's.

Key concepts

- **Neurodegenerative diseases cause neural cell death, disability, dependency, significantly shorten life expectancy and are, to date, incurable. In Spain, it is calculated that they affect between 1 and 1.5 million people.**
- **Increased life expectancy goes hand in hand with a very significant increase in the cases of diseases like Alzheimer's, Parkinson's and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), which has an impact on both planning and budgets for public policies in healthcare and social welfare.**
- **The risk of developing these diseases is influenced by genetic factors, the environment, lifestyle and the interaction of these factors over time, although the weight of each one is still not fully understood. Changing lifestyle or reducing risk factors that can be modified during determined stages of life could reduce the risk of developing these diseases. By doing this, it is estimated that over a third of all dementia cases could be prevented or have a delayed onset.**
- **These disorders are often not detected at early stages. Although early diagnosis is a serious setback for the patient and their family, it can also bring many medical advantages (more effective early interventions to alleviate or hold back symptoms) and social (medical, legal and care planning) if the necessary support exists. Techniques currently exist for the specific diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease and multiple sclerosis, although access to these services is different in each of Spain's autonomous communities. In the near future, conditions like Alzheimer's disease could be detected with a simple blood test.**
- **Treatments already exist that can hold back multiple sclerosis or control the most incapacitating symptoms of Parkinson's disease. For different diseases many of the symptoms, which vary or accumulate over years, can be treated with drugs or specific interventions. Although emerging treatments can hold back the progression of Alzheimer's for some months and represent a step forward, the cost-benefit ratio is not clear in terms of patient autonomy, so Europe is debating their approval and funding by National Health Systems.**
- **Social costs are higher than those of medical care and increase with the severity and length of these diseases. In most cases it is the family who has to cope, which highlights the need to develop a sustainable, specialist professional care system. Comprehensive healthcare requires greater coordination between the social welfare and healthcare fields to improve the inclusion and wellbeing of both patients and their families.**

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